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Different phases for EV Power Quality; a business case

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Summary

Smart and seamless charging cannot be taken for granted. In 2019, consumers still become frustrated when their electric vehicle (EV) unexpectedly charges slower than expected. Network operators on their account are concerned about imbalance in the network due to the uptake in the roll out of charging stations, and about charging points that cause interference disturbances in their grid. Lack of regulations is the cause, which leads to cheap, less robust design choices in both the EV and the charging station. Subsequent solutions often prove to be expensive and complex. Making agreements with vehicle manufacturers and charging station providers can prevent consumers from having to incur unexpected expenses and disruptions of electricity supply.

With this paper, ElaadNL wants to draw attention to the power quality issues potentially caused by EV-charging and to make a number of proposals for improvement. For the Dutch market, but also lessons can be learned for other countries. This way the number of satisfied, fully charged EV drivers can continue to grow and the electricity networks remains in balance.

Keywords: Power Quality, EV, smart charging, supraharmonics, regulation

1 What is going on: scale up and maturity problems

Electrification of transportation is scaling up in the Netherlands, but also in many other countries. Every year the number of electric vehicles and charging stations is increasing faster. Consumers and grid operators (DSO¹) are now discovering that there are major differences in charging technology in vehicles and charging points. Some grid connections lead to higher connection costs, both for the customer and the grid operator, slower charging and disruptions to the electricity grid. For example: Various connections are already prohibited in Germany².

2 From alternating current to direct current

The electricity grid in Europe is largely three-phase alternating current (AC). This means that a connection can have three cables through which electricity is supplied. A battery needs direct current (DC) to charge. At some point this alternating current will have to be converted to direct current.

This conversion takes place in a so-called inverter. This inverter can be integrated in the car, the charging station or both. This conversion takes place in the vehicle itself when using a regular AC-charging station and in the charging station when using a fast (DC) charger.

¹ Distribution system operator

² Paragraph 14 of the German EnWG

Fig. 1. Business case single phase charging

3 Single – or three phase: advantages and disadvantages

An EV manufacturer can choose to install a single-phase or three-phase inverter in his vehicle. The single-phase inverter delivers cost benefits and weight savings for the manufacturer. For the EV driver, the vehicle is cheaper at purchase, but much slower at charging. However, most regular charging stations in the Netherlands can deliver 16 Amps per socket (and therefore 11 kW of power) on all three phases. When using a single-phase charger, the charging speed will be limited to only 3.7 kW, or approximately 18 KM driving distance per hour.

Fig. 2. Business case single phase charging

A fully discharged electric vehicle with an 80 kWh battery will then take no less than 22 hours to fully charge. If the vehicle has a three-phase charger, this is reduced to just over 7 hours.

Fig. 3. Business case three phase charging

In the Netherlands, three-phase charging does not have to cost much more for the customer; the tariff that the network operator charges for a single-phase 40 Amp connection and one of 3x 25 Amp is the same (approximately € 250 per year). Only the possible costs for changing the connection (€ 280) and the additional costs for a three-phase charging station (approximately € 250) are required as an investment in the Netherlands. See also the visualization.

4 Quick fix doesn't work

In order to achieve a faster charging speed, some EV manufacturers put a faster single-phase inverter in the vehicle. With for example a 32 Amp inverter, the vehicle charges twice as fast. However, not all regular, public charging stations can deliver this and home charging at this speed requires either a heavier grid connection, with the rate almost quadrupled (approximately € 950 per year in the Netherlands), or a compact DC charger of several thousand euros. In both cases, the customer must be in the pouch.

Moreover, this charging method is unfavorable for the electricity grid. The grid is disproportionately burdened, with more electricity being used on one phase than on the other. This can cause problems with the electricity supply and lead to potentially dangerous situations.

Fig 3. Unbalanced cables in an electricity grid³

5 Supraharmonics

Standards already exist for inverters to prevent distortions in the grid [2][3][4].

³ Credits for Envia Mitteldeutsche Energie AG for this illustration

Without compliance with those requirements, inrush currents can occur that potentially switch off energy supply. These requirements also prevent harmonic currents that are potentially dangerous, lead to energy losses and excessive heating of electric motors and electronic equipment. However, there are no standards yet for so-called "supraharmonics", distortions with a frequency above the regular harmonics. Most inverters, either from EV, PV or fast DC-chargers are a source of Supraharmonics, which influences the reliability of the grid and all equipment connected to it.

Fig 6. The effect of multiple EV's and supra harmonics

With supraharmonics, the inverter emits high-frequency currents, which can cause additional heat losses, capacity reduction of the grid, charging problems and a shortened servicelife of electronic equipment.

5 The call for regulation

To ensure that electric driving continues to grow optimally, ElaadNL and the Dutch Ministry of Transport, Public Works and Water Management are asking the Ministry of Economic Affairs to charge electric vehicles on a three-phase basis as standard. The costs of better charging technology outweigh the benefits: a robust electricity network and a higher charging speed. In our opinion this call is broader and should be a call for European regulation, or even a global standard.

Further more, extra requirements should be imposed on inverters in order to prevent heat losses, network capacity reduction, charging problems and a shortened service life of electronic equipment. A question to be answered is that the EV should be tested and certified on charging technology, but by whom? The road authority? Should it be considered as electric equipment like your washing machine?

Acknowledgments

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References

- [1] <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0037940/2019-07-10>
- [2] EN 50160 characterises voltage parameters of electrical energy in public distribution systems. This is a European standard but it is supplemented in some regions or countries by other supplemental standards, such as national gridcodes
- [3] IEC 61000-3-12:2011 deals with the limitation of harmonic currents injected into the public supply system. The limits given in this International Standard are applicable to electrical and electronic equipment with a rated input current exceeding 16 A and up to and including 75 A per phase, intended to be connected to public low-voltage a.c. distribution systems
- [4] IEC 61000-4-2:2008 relates to the immunity requirements and test methods for electrical and electronic equipment subjected to static electricity discharges, from operators directly, and from personnel to adjacent objects. It additionally defines ranges of test levels which relate to different environmental and installation conditions and establishes test procedures. The object of IEC 61000-4-2:2008 is to establish a common and

reproducible basis for evaluating the performance of electrical and electronic equipment when subjected to electrostatic discharges.

Authors

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Arjan Wargers received a MSc degree in 2001 from the University of Groningen, Netherlands. Currently he is employed as Manager Innovation Electric Mobility at ElaadNL and as Innovator at Dutch DSO Enexis. Since 2010, his main research interests are in the field of Electric Vehicles, primarily aimed at grid integration of EV, Smart Charging and EV related protocols. He is a driving force behind the innovation and practical research executed at ElaadNL over the last 10 years.